

Simple methods of detection of a few ions in the presence of other ones of similar nature in qualitative analysis

Anupam Chakraborty and A. K. Chakravarti*

61, Anjangerh, Birati, Kolkata-700 051, India

Manuscript received 27 November 2006, revised 25 June 2007, accepted 6 September 2007

Keywords : Detection, arsenate, bromine, chemical education.

The present communication introduces some common chemical reactions in qualitative chemical analysis for the detection of some ions in the presence of alike ions with easily available, cheap, pollution-free reagents and hazardless techniques. The tests referred to here have been repeatedly demonstrated by the present authors while conducting chemistry practical classes, and the students carried out the tests successfully for the detection of the following ions.

Detection of arsenate in the presence of phosphate :

It is known that,

- (1) Phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) in strongly nitric acid medium produces a yellow precipitate, $[(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{PO}_4 \cdot (\text{Mo}_{12}\text{O}_{36})]$, with ammonium molybdate reagent, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{MoO}_4$, at cold or gentle warm condition. Under similar acidic condition arsenate (AsO_4^{3-}) produces similar precipitate, $[(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{AsMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]$, but on boiling.
- (2) A mixture of phosphate, arsenate and arsenite in neutral or ammoniacal solution can be separated by magnesia mixture (a solution of MgCl_2 , NH_4Cl and NH_4OH) and then detected. Arsenite in the presence of phosphate can be directly detected in hydrochloric acid medium by passing H_2S gas (or adding aqueous solution of sodium sulphide) when yellow precipitate of As_2S_3 is immediately formed. In a mixture of phosphate and arsenate, the former can be detected in the presence of the latter using HNO_3 and ammonium molybdate reagent at cold and shaking. Tartaric acid may be added to mask AsO_4^{3-} .

However, so far no direct method of detection of arsenate in the presence of phosphate in solution is described. In relation to this the following methods are suggested.

After detection of PO_4^{3-} in the solution (3–4 ml) by the above method, regardless of its presence, arsenate can be detected in another 3–4 ml of the same solution through its reduction to arsenite by I^- , N_2H_5^+ or ascorbic acid (in the presence of phosphate too) and formation of As_2S_3 . The related reduction potentials are^{1,2} :

(Dehydro- (Ascorbate)
ascorbic acid)

(Dehydro (1-Ascorbic acid)
l-ascorbic acid)

The methods :

To 3–4 ml solution of the mixture of AsO_4^{3-} and PO_4^{3-} (aqueous solution or Na_2CO_3 extract acidified with dil. HCl or dil. HNO_3 solution evaporated and taken up with dil. HCl) 8–10 drops of conc. HCl is added, shaken well. It is then treated with a small quantity of solid KI (0.1–0.2 g). I_2 is liberated and the solution becomes I_2 -red coloured. This colour is discharged through dropwise addition of dilute aqueous solution of Na_2SO_3 (excess solution is better to avoid), or to the mixture 0.2–0.3 g hydrazine-hydrochloride, or hydrazine-sulphate, or ascorbic acid is added, warmed and shaken. Then H_2S gas is passed, or aqueous solution of Na -sulphide is added in any of the resulting solutions. Yellow precipitate of As_2S_3 is formed.

Reactions :

For the presence of Cu^{2+} (in dil. HCl or H_2SO_4), in the first method, I_2 is liberated by both the AsO_4^{3-} and the Cu^{2+} ions ($2Cu^{2+} + 4I^- \rightleftharpoons Cu_2I_2 + I_2$). The latter forms white, insoluble Cu_2I_2 together with I_2 . It is separated by filtration. The I_2 -red filtrate is decolourised by dilute Na_2SO_3 solution and then H_2S gas is passed, or Na-sulphide solution is added – yellow As_2S_3 is precipitated.

The other method is to use ascorbic acid (instead of KI) and warming. To the solution then excess NH_4SCN solution is added. $CuSCN$ precipitates. It is shaken, allowed to settle and then filtered. To the clear filtrate H_2S gas is passed, or Na-sulphide solution is added – yellow As_2S_3 precipitates. $N_2H_5^+$, instead of ascorbic acid is not so efficient.

In all of the above methods PO_4^{3-} remains unreacted.

Besides the above wet methods, some other reactions related to dry tests may be applied. In relation to this the following are to be considered.

- (i) Any arsenic compound in contact with metallic zinc (dust) and dilute H_2SO_4 (~4 N) liberates arsine (AsH_3) which has garlic odour and turns $HgCl_2$ solution-soaked filter paper yellow to brown to black.
- (ii) Except arsenate (AsO_4^{3-}) other arsenic compounds in contact with aluminium (dust) or zinc-aluminium (dust mixture) and concentrated KOH or NaOH solution (~2 N) liberates arsine.
- (iii) PO_4^{3-} does not produce phosphine (PH_3) by any of the above reactions ((i) and (ii)). So, in the presence of PO_4^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , AsO_3^{3-} or As_2O_3 etc. can be detected applying the above reactions properly.
- (iv) However, if sulphide is present together with arsenic compound, in the reaction (i) above, H_2S will be liberated along with arsine (AsH_3). The former can be detected by holding Pb-acetate or alkaline nitroprusside solution-soaked paper at the liberated gas which do not react with arsine. $HgCl_2$ solution-paper will react with both H_2S and AsH_3 ; H_2S and AsH_3 do not react to form As_2S_3 . In the mixture of

both the gases, H_2S and AsH_3 , the latter can be detected after absorbing the former completely in a suitable way, viz. passing through a concentrated NaOH solution, or Pb-acetate solution, or through a suspended $CdCO_3$ solution.

- (v) For any arsenic compound other than AsO_4^{3-} , together with sulphide, reaction (ii) above can be applied. However, if any NH_4^+ -salt, NO_2^- or NO_3^- is present together with As-compound, NH_3 gas along with AsH_3 will be liberated. For detection of AsH_3 , $HgCl_2$ solution-soaked paper may be used.

A sure method of detection of bromine produced from bromide or bromate in qualitative analysis

In the preliminary tests for bromide or bromate, bromine (yellow or orange vapour) is produced through oxidation of Br^- . Due to its colour Br_2 -vapour is very often confusing with NO_2 (from NO_2^- or NO_3^- in the sample) and chromyl chloride, CrO_2Cl_2 (from CrO_4^{2-} or $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and Cl^- together in the sample).

In order to avoid the confusion and to be sure for bromine, the authors suggest the vapour to pass into "aniline-water" (mentioned below) in a test tube which produces immediately a heavy white precipitate of 2,4,6-tribromo aniline. NO_2 has no noticeable effect, CrO_2Cl_2 may turn the solution yellowish but no precipitate formation (excess Br_2 -vapour may turn the solution yellowish but together with white precipitate which forms first). Cl_2 -gas or I_2 -vapour do not form any such compound with aniline.

The test is very simple, harmless and easily performable. The reagent, "aniline-water" may be prepared in large quantities with almost no cost and can be stored in a stoppered bottle for long days.

Preparation of aniline-water: To 2 to 3 drops of aniline taken in a 500 ml beaker, 5–6 ml of concentrated HCl is added, stirred well and then diluted with distilled water to 200–250 ml. Before use of this solution, 2–3 ml in a test-tube may be diluted further to 6–8 ml with distilled water.

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate the earnestness of the students who urged for publication of these methods for the benefit of greater number of students.

References

1. "Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Table F.1, James E. Huheey, Harper International SI Edition, 1983.
2. "Analytical Application of Complex Equilibria", Sec. 4.3 – Organic Redox Systems, J. Incze'dy, Ellis Horwood Ltd., 1976.